
AN ILP SOLUTION FOR MINIMAL REPRESENTATIVE SUBSET SELECTION

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ABSTRACT

We present an integer linear programming (ILP) formulation for minimal representative subset selection via neighborhood coverage on directed k -nearest-neighbor (k-NN) graphs. Given pairwise distances between samples, such as whole-slide images (WSIs) in a histopathology cohort, we seek the smallest subset such that every sample is either selected or lies among the top- k nearest neighbors of at least one selected sample. This problem generalizes the minimum dominating set and set cover formulations. It is an NP-hard problem but solvable efficiently on practical datasets using modern ILP solvers. We outline the formulation, describe neighborhood construction, discuss related problems and the complexity, provide a minimal working example, and include concise implementation notes and code pointers.

1 Motivation & Overview

A common challenge with large datasets is selecting a *small yet representative* subset for curation, visualization, labeling, and benchmarking. We therefore pose a minimal *representative subset selection* problem: given pairwise distances between samples, choose the fewest exemplars so that every sample is either selected or is sufficiently close to at least one selected sample [1, 2].

We define “close” using directed k -nearest-neighbor (k-NN) neighborhoods constructed from the distance matrix. This view yields a clean graph formulation and a compact optimization model. In particular, the problem specializes to a *dominating-set* problem on a directed k-NN graph and, equivalently, a *set-cover* instance over k-NN neighborhoods. As a result, the problem is NP-hard in general. Nevertheless, modern mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) solvers such as COIN-OR Branch and Cut (CBC) [3] can handle moderate-sized instances efficiently in practice, even though the problem is NP-hard [4].

While our case study uses whole slide images from pathology, the formulation applies to any collection embedded in a metric or learned feature space, such as image, text, or multimodal embeddings. The goal of this note is to present a concise and broadly applicable ILP-based solution.

2 Problem Definition & ILP Formulation

Setup Let the samples be indexed by $V = \{1, \dots, n\}$. Let $d(i, j)$ denote a distance (smaller is closer) computed in a learned or metric space. For each $i \in V$, define the (directed) top- k neighborhood

$$N_k(i) \subseteq V \setminus \{i\}$$

as the set of the k closest indices to i under $d(i, \cdot)$. Note $N_k(i)$ need not be symmetric: $j \in N_k(i)$ does not imply $i \in N_k(j)$. For each target $j \in V$, define its *incoming coverage set*

$$C(j) = \{i \in V : j \in N_k(i)\},$$

i.e., the indices that would cover j if selected.

Coverage requirement A subset $S \subseteq V$ is *feasible* if every $j \in V$ is either selected ($j \in S$) or covered by a selected in-neighbor ($C(j) \cap S \neq \emptyset$). Our objective is to find a feasible S of minimal cardinality.

ILP variables Introduce binary variables $x_i \in \{0, 1\}$ indicating selection: $x_i = 1$ iff i is in the representative set.

ILP objective Minimize the number of selected samples:

$$\min \sum_{i \in V} x_i.$$

Coverage constraints For each $j \in V$, enforce that j is either selected or covered by at least one selected in-neighbor:

$$x_j + \sum_{i \in C(j)} x_i \geq 1, \quad \forall j \in V. \quad (1)$$

Compact ILP Putting it together:

$$\begin{aligned} \min \quad & \sum_{i \in V} x_i \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & x_j + \sum_{i \in C(j)} x_i \geq 1, \quad \forall j \in V, \\ & x_i \in \{0, 1\}, \quad \forall i \in V. \end{aligned}$$

3 Related Problems & Complexity

Minimum dominating set view Form a directed graph G on V with an arc $i \rightarrow j$ whenever $j \in N_k(i)$. A subset $S \subseteq V$ is said to *dominate* G if every node $j \in V$ is either selected itself ($j \in S$) or is pointed to by at least one selected node $i \in S$. The coverage constraints $x_j + \sum_{i \in C(j)} x_i \geq 1$ enforce exactly this condition, so our ILP is a minimum dominating set problem on the directed k -nearest-neighbor graph. Since the minimum dominating set problem is NP-complete even for undirected graphs [1, 4], our problem is NP-hard as well.

Set cover view Define one set for each $i \in V$ as $S_i = \{i\} \cup N_k(i)$, representing the elements that would be covered if sample i is selected. The universe to be covered is V . Selecting representatives is therefore equivalent to choosing a subcollection of these sets $\{S_i\}$ whose union equals V , a classical *minimum set cover* problem [2]. In our formulation each representative has equal cost (the unweighted case), but a more general *weighted set cover* can be obtained by assigning nonnegative costs w_i and minimizing $\sum_i w_i x_i$ [5, 6].

Complexity and approximation The representative subset selection problem is NP-hard because it generalizes both minimum dominating set and minimum set cover. Modern solvers such as the CBC engine, however, combine linear programming relaxations, branch-and-bound search, and cutting planes to prune most of the search space in practice. For structured, sparse instances like ours, where each constraint involves at most $k+1$ variables, CBC typically converges quickly to an optimal or near-optimal solution, even though the theoretical worst-case complexity remains exponential.

4 Implementation notes

MILP implementation We implement the ILP using Python package PuLP with its CBC solver [3, 7]. Each sample i is assigned a binary variable $x_i \in \{0, 1\}$, and the objective minimizes $\sum_i x_i$, the total number of selected samples. For every sample j , we enforce a coverage constraint

$$x_j + \sum_{i \in C(j)} x_i \geq 1,$$

so that each sample is either selected or covered by at least one selected neighbor. The reverse coverage sets $C(j) = \{i : j \in N_k(i)\}$ are built from the top- k neighbor lists in $O(nk)$ time. The resulting model has n binary variables and n constraints, each involving at most $k+1$ terms. The model is solved with CBC using default settings. A time limit can be specified for large datasets, and a feasible solution is always returned even if the optimality gap remains.

WSI recipe For the whole-slide image (WSI) setting, we extract slide embeddings, compute pairwise distances, construct $N_k(i)$ and the corresponding $C(j)$, then call the ILP solver to select representative slides. The output includes the selected slide IDs, total number of slides n , neighborhood size k , and optionally summary statistics such as runtime and solution size $|S|$.

5 Minimal working example

Consider $n = 6$ with $k = 2$:

$$\begin{aligned} N_2(1) &= \{2, 3\}, & N_2(2) &= \{1, 3\}, & N_2(3) &= \{2, 4\}, \\ N_2(4) &= \{3, 5\}, & N_2(5) &= \{4, 6\}, & N_2(6) &= \{5, 4\}. \end{aligned}$$

Then $C(3) = \{1, 2, 4\}$. One optimal solution is $S = \{2, 5\}$, which covers all elements.

6 Code & Availability

We provide a minimal implementation that constructs $N_k(i)$ from a distance matrix, builds $C(j)$, and solves the ILP in Python with PuLP and CBC [3, 7]. Code is available at https://github.com/haoranch3n/ilp_solution.

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